

Arguing with Corpora

The Epistemic Status of Corpora in Computational Humanities

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There is hardly any research in digital and computational humanities that does not use a corpus of some sort. Indeed, the centrality of corpora seems one of the most obvious differences between “traditional” and computational humanities. Despite this centrality of corpora, there is surprisingly little theoretical discussion of corpora and their epistemological impact. Our work aims to address this gap by investigating how corpora are being used to craft arguments—and to tell stories—in computational humanities research.

Our starting point is the observation that a quantitative analysis of a corpus on its own can only give us insights on the corpus itself. If we find that the number of occurrences of X is higher than that of Y , this is all we learn, that in this corpus, X is more frequent than Y , nothing else. However, the humanities are not interested in corpora as abstract objects. The humanities are primarily concerned with qualitative, “why?” questions. The corpus must thus stand for something else, which is the *actual* research object.

Indeed, Piotrowski (2019) notes that a corpus should be considered a *model* of the research object. The question then is how the model relates to the research object. Because *if* a quantitative analysis of a corpus—which is, again, *not* the actual research object, and, following Apostel (1961, 36), neither directly nor indirectly interacting with it—warrants making arguments about the actual research object, there must be some (epistemological) justification for this. The hypothesis for the work described in this contribution is that we should be able to glean some of this justification from research articles that use corpora to construct scholarly arguments.

We are ultimately interested in formalizing the scholarly discourse following Jean-Claude Gardin’s *logician approach* (Gardin 1991); however, as Gardin et al. (1987) show, its application to actual scholarly publications is much harder than it may appear at first sight. What we describe here is thus only a first step and part of ongoing research. To get an impression of current practices, we selected a number of recent articles (published between 2022 and 2025) from the *Journal of Cultural Analytics* (JCA) covering a variety of topics, ranging from visual culture to literature to biographical archives, etc. We considered sampling from different journals, e.g., *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* (DSH), *Humanités numériques*, *Zeitschrift für digitale Geisteswissenschaften* (ZfDG), *Umanistica Digitale*, or *Digital Studies/Le champ numérique* (DSCN), but ultimately restricted ourselves to JCA because of its aims and scope as a “foundational publishing venue [...] interested in how computational methods combined with cultural artifacts create and contribute to new knowledge and diverse perspectives.”¹ Methodologically, research published in JCA appears to be more homogenous in its approach, compared to more “generalist” DH journals: it is most often based on corpora, and selected based on the arguments they craft. Limiting ourselves to recent JCA articles also ensures that all articles were peer-reviewed according to the same criteria and are thus part of the current culture of inquiry.

We carefully reviewed the selected articles using an approach based on literary close reading. Literary close reading refers to a slow, purposeful, analytical, and meditative form of reading that often includes annotation, note-taking, and painstaking attention to detail. We carried out a word-by-word examination to carefully consider the texts’ “language, content, structure, patterns”² to uncover the

¹Journal of Cultural Analytics

²ClassicsWrites: Close Reading

logical argumentation. This highly granular and intentional approach is justified by the recognition that we need a more nuanced interpretation of authors' chains of arguments than what is currently possible to do automatically. The interpretation of rhetorical structures is always subjective; for example it depends on a reader's prior knowledge whether a statement is considered as part of an argument or merely as background information (see, e.g., [Das et al. 2017](#)). [Hayles \(2010\)](#) suggests that close reading has its place in a synergistic approach with other reading forms including "hyper" and "machine" (e.g., distant) reading.

In this contribution, due to space constraints, we only consider a subset of three articles ([Arnold et al. 2023](#); [Grisot and Herrmann 2023](#); [Berensmeyer and Trurnit 2022](#)) from our corpus to illustrate how authors construct and quantitatively analyse their large-scale cultural corpora, and how they interpret the results of their quantitative analyses in light of existing literary and cultural theories. The selection of just three articles is necessarily subjective, but we aimed at striking a balance between similarity and diversity: the articles all fall within the general area of literary studies, but focus on different aspects of literature.

The typical approach, also used by the authors of the three articles, is to first produce quantitative analyses of their respective corpora in the hope of eventually identifying general patterns. These results are then interpreted in a humanities fashion, but without directly referring back to the research objects in question. Instead, quantitative observations tend to be interpreted in light of existing interpretations from the humanities—e.g., historical facts, aesthetic concepts, and literary theories that were already established when the corpora were constructed. As such, we find indeed that authors' interpretations often reflect properties of the corpus itself, rather than the phenomenon under study, which is typically *external* to the corpus. For example, when studying literary topoi via the way they manifest in a textual corpus, one has to keep in mind that topoi exist as cultural phenomena beyond the corpus at hand.

We argue that the corpora-based argumentation process observed in many studies, including the three studies considered here, produces insights that (i) confirm existing interpretations, and/or (ii) explain statistical observations as symptomatic of or in terms of a conjectured relation to an overarching concept or theme. This constitutes a disjunctive moment in the argumentation: insights do not emerge from or illuminate the objects themselves. When arguments fail to verify whether insights hold at the individual object-level, all the while positing that quantitative observations are symptomatic of an overarching concept, theme, or idea, a question is raised about the epistemic status of the corpus. We sense that (iii) the corpus as such is influencing interpretations ([Piotrowski \(2024\)](#) even argues that corpora are *phenomenotechnical devices* ([Bachelard \[1934\] 1968](#)) that *produce* the phenomenon to be studied). Ultimately, while concepts are operationalized into quantitative methods that produce adequate quantitative observations, we observe a (iv) lack of verification of operationalization at the level of the object.

Our aim is obviously to look beyond the three studies at hand and to probe into what we think may be a deeper issue: the unclear epistemic status of the corpus and the nature of the insights it affords. One important task will be to identify exemplary studies in which the the corpus and the phenomenon under study are aligned and explicated, allowing the authors to produce interpretations that yield novel insights and allow for strong arguments.

We argue that clarifying the role of corpora is essential for strengthening the theoretical foundations of the field and making computational humanities research both more rigorous and more relevant to the humanities. By disentangling the phenomenon under study from the corpus, the corpus can be seen as a model of (or phenomenotechnical device creating) the phenomenon. This is the first step towards understanding what insights the corpus can afford; with the long term goal of producing research that deepens our knowledge of the phenomena studied by the humanities.

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